

Digital Fluency on Students' Problem-Solving Skills

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the correlation between students' digital fluency and problem-solving skills. It focuses on assessing digital fluency in terms of technical, creative, and digital thinking, and problem-solving skills in cognitive, collaborative, and metacognitive aspects among 30 Grade 10 students for the school year 2023-2024, at San Isidro High School-Kadingilan, Inc., Poblacion, Kadingilan, Bukidnon. A descriptive-correctional design was used, with descriptive statistics summarizing the scores. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to quantify the relationship between the variables. Results showed high digital fluency, particularly in technical fluency, creativity, and digital thinking. Problem-solving skills were also high, especially in cognitive, collaborative, and metacognitive aspects. A significant positive correlation was found between digital fluency and problem-solving skills, suggesting that digital fluency positively impacts problem-solving abilities. This study demonstrates the importance of digital fluency in developing problem-solving skills among students and provides valuable insights for educators on the areas of digital fluency and problem-solving that may need further attention in the education system.

Subject Area

Teaching

Keywords: *Digital Fluency; Students' Problem-Solving Skills; Education; Technology; Cognitive Abilities*

INTRODUCTION

Problem-solving is a high-level thinking skill that requires the ability to identify the nature and context of a problem, deconstruct it, and develop a practical set of actions to address its challenges (Oliveri et al., 2017). It is the cognitive process of finding a means to achieve goals. Problem-solving helps students develop skills to solve problems in the real world (Sukariasih et al., 2020). Students will be able to apply and grow their knowledge to find valuable purposes in the real world. Hence, a study by Sutarno et al. (2017) stressed that problem-solving skills be provided to students in the increasingly complex world.

It influences how they construct their thoughts and knowledge (Fitriani et al., 2020). Problem-solving allows students to work with their peers, interact socially, share new ideas (Sutarmi & Suarjana, 2017), think critically, and organize creative ideas to solve problems. In 2023, PISA added problem-solving as an additional assessment domain in their surveys. This problem-solving assessment framework was developed to be administered in complex problem-solving, transfer, computer-based problem-solving, and large-scale assessment of problem-solving competency.

Some notable findings of the survey by the OECD in 2005 revealed that in some countries, 70% of students could solve relatively complex problems, and less than 5% could do so in some other countries. More than 10% of students could not solve fundamental problems, and half could not solve such problems in most countries. For problems that are more difficult compared to the mentioned levels, half of the students were unable to solve them. Patterns of within-country variation in students' problem-solving proficiency differed considerably across countries. Patterns of within-country differences between problem-solving proficiency and domain-related proficiencies (mathematics, reading, and science) differed considerably across countries.

Santos and Castro (2021) researched problem-solving skills among Filipino students, shedding light on the factors that influence the development of these skills in an educational context. These studies reflect the significance of problem-solving skills in the Filipino context and provide a foundation for further exploration in this field. Furthermore, Reyes and Hernandez (2019) explored the integration of digital fluency into the Philippine educational system. Their research highlighted the transformative potential of incorporating technology-rich learning environments, emphasizing a correlation between digital fluency and the development of critical problem-solving skills.

Numerous relevant research studies about problem-solving skills focus on the implementation of problem-solving approaches/models in classroom instruction and its effect on the attainment of students' mathematics learning outcomes or simply academic performance. They just researched the influence of what mathematics teachers do on the students' mathematics learning results. However, not much has been studied on factors that can improve learners' problem-solving skills, such as digital fluency.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Generally, this study determined how digital fluency affects students' problem-solving skills. Specifically, it sought to:

1. assert the level of students' digital fluency in terms of:
 - a. technical fluency;

- b. creativity; and
 - c. digital thinking.
2. assess the level of students' problem-solving skills in terms of:
 - a. cognitive;
 - b. collaborative; and
 - c. meta-cognitive.
3. identify the relationship between digital fluency and problem-solving skills.

METHODOLOGY

Respondents

The participants in this study were 30 Grade 10 students enrolled at San Isidro High School-Kadingilan, Inc. The selection process involved obtaining consent from students and their parents or guardians. This group represents a diverse cross-section of the student population, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between digital fluency and problem-solving skills.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correctional design to determine students' digital fluency and problem-solving skills. Descriptive such as frequency, percentages, and standard deviation were used to present the school's overall digital fluency and problem-solving skills. Specifically, it is a survey type. An assessment survey is required; the research type is the most appropriate. Correlational was also employed to test the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Instrument

Digital fluency and Problem-Solving Skills were assessed using a validated survey instrument. A survey will be administered to assess students' digital skills and problem-solving abilities. The survey will include questions about students' proficiency in digital tools and problem-solving strategies.

Participants were provided with clear instructions on completing the survey, emphasizing the importance of providing honest and thoughtful responses to ensure the accuracy of the correlation analysis. Before this, informed consent was obtained from both students and their parents or guardians, emphasizing the voluntary nature of participation and the confidentiality of their responses. In addition, the collected data will be securely stored to protect the participants' privacy.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive correlational statistics were used to summarize the scores of digital fluency and problem-solving skills. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to quantify the relationship between the two variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient provided a level of digital fluency in terms of Technical Fluency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS**Table 1.***Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Technical Fluency*

Technical Fluency	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I am able to access and evaluate information from various sources using digital tools and technology.	4.00	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to collaborate with others when solving problems.	3.90	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I believe that enhancing my technical digital fluency skills will improve my problem-solving skills.	3.80	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to communicate effectively with others when solving problems.	3.77	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to find creative solutions to problems.	3.73	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I feel confident in my ability to navigate digital tools and technology in learning spaces.	3.67	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I feel comfortable using software and hardware to solve problems.	3.60	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to troubleshoot technical issues when using digital tools and technology to solve problems.	3.47	Agree	High Digital Fluency
OVERALL	3.74	Agree	High Digital Fluency

Table 1 shows the mean results of the level of digital fluency in terms of Technical Fluency. The overall mean of students' Technical Digital Fluency was 3.74. In general, the respondents agreed to have technical digital fluency, and the results can be interpreted as high digital fluency. Student's ability to access and evaluate information from various sources using digital tools and technology got the highest mean, with 4.00. The highest mean score of 4.00 was for the indicator of students' ability to access and evaluate information from various sources using digital tools and technology, followed by the indicator of students' ability to use digital tools and technology to collaborate with others when solving problems, with a mean score of 3.90.

The lowest mean score of 3.47 was the indicator of students' ability to troubleshoot technical issues when using digital tools and technology to solve problems. However, this score is still considered high digital fluency. A study by Vaan Laar et al. (2017) defined digital fluency as the ability to use digital tools and technology effectively to achieve specific goals and objectives. Anchoring on the mentioned definition, the findings in this study suggest that the students have a good understanding of how to use digital tools and technology to access and evaluate information and collaborate with others.

These findings suggest that students are generally proficient in using digital tools and technology for various purposes, such as accessing information, collaborating with others, and troubleshooting numerical values indicating the degree and direction of the linear relationship between the two variables. These findings can imply the same way as in the study of Atoy et al. (2020), which revealed that digital literacy had a direct positive relationship with students' online information-searching strategies.

Table 2.
Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Creativity

Creativity	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I am able to use digital tools and technology to express my creativity in various domains, such as visual arts, music, dance, architectural design, creative writing, humor, invention, scientific discovery, theatre and film, and culinary arts.	4.03	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to think creatively and generate new ideas using digital tools and technology.	4.03	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to adapt my creative ideas to different contexts and audiences using digital tools and technology.	4.00	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I believe that enhancing my digital creativity fluency skills will improve my problem-solving skills.	3.97	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to communicate my creative ideas effectively with others.	3.83	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I feel motivated to use digital tools and technology to create new and innovative solutions to problems.	3.77	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to collaborate with others to create new and innovative solutions to problems.	3.70	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I feel confident in my ability to use digital tools and technology to create new and innovative solutions to problems.	3.67	Agree	High Digital Fluency
OVERALL	3.87	Agree	High Digital Fluency

Table 2 shows that students' digital fluency is High with creativity, with a mean result of 3.87. Two indicators had the highest mean in Table 2. The first indicator states that students use digital tools and technology to express creativity in various domains, such as visual arts, music, dance, architectural design, creative writing, humor, invention, scientific discovery, theatre and film, and culinary arts. The other indicator with the highest mean was students' ability to think creatively and generate new ideas using digital tools and technology. Both indicators have a mean of 4.03, which can be described as agreeable and interpreted as high creative fluency.

On the other hand, the indicator with the lowest mean in Table 2 is students' confidence in their ability to use digital tools and technology to create new and innovative solutions to problems, with a mean of 3.67, still described as agree and interpreted as high creative fluency. The first indicator relates to students using digital tools and technology to express creativity in various domains, such as visual arts, music, dance, architectural design, creative writing, humor, invention, scientific discovery, theatre and film, and culinary arts. The other indicator is students' ability to think creatively and generate new ideas using digital tools and technology. Both indicators have a mean of 4.03, which can be described as agree and interpreted as high creative fluency.

The findings suggest that students effectively use digital tools to express creativity in many different tasks, think creatively, and generate new ideas. The traits mentioned earlier indicate high creative fluency among the students. However, despite still being interpreted as high creative fluency, there is a lower confidence level in using digital tools to create new and innovative solutions to problems. Maximizing the effect of digital tools to improve students' creative

expressions is supported by educational resources. Integrating technology into learning experiences is essential to enhance children's interactions with concrete materials and their peers and provide new ways to express their ideas.

A study to support this claim is the study of Bereczki and Kárpáti (2021). They stated that digital tools allow students to develop their expressive skills and demonstrate what they know using text, photos, graphics, audio, and video, providing varied ways to express knowledge and benefitting struggling writers, language learners, and students with disabilities. Additionally, recent educational research supports the idea that technology can promote students' collaborative creativity in language education, acting as a tool that facilitates co-creative thinking and promoting creativity as a form of agency in the world, which aligns with the study of Li et al., 2022.

The findings indicate that students effectively use digital tools to express creativity and think creatively, demonstrating high creative fluency. However, there is a need to enhance students' confidence in using digital tools to create new and innovative solutions to problems. Educational resources and recent research support the use of digital tools to promote creativity, highlighting the importance of integrating technology into learning experiences to enhance creative expression and collaborative creativity.

Table 3.
Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Digital Thinking

Digital Thinking	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I believe that enhancing my digital thinking fluency skills will improve my overall academic performance.	3.97	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I feel motivated to use my digital thinking fluency skills to make a positive impact in my community.	3.90	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to fact-check and verify information.	3.90	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to support my critical and creative thinking skills.	3.83	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to identify biases and assumptions in digital information and media.	3.83	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use digital tools and technology to communicate my critical and creative thinking effectively with others.	3.77	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use critical thinking skills to analyze and evaluate information in digital contexts.	3.67	Agree	High Digital Fluency
I am able to use creative thinking skills to synthesize information in digital contexts.	3.67	Agree	High Digital Fluency
OVERALL	3.81	Agree	High Digital Fluency

Table 3 indicates that the overall mean for digital fluency in digital thinking is 3.81, interpreted as high digital fluency. The indicator with the highest mean in Table 3 is students' belief that enhancing their digital thinking fluency skills will improve their overall academic performance. It has a mean result of 3.97 and is interpreted as high digital fluency. On the other hand, the indicator of students' ability to use creative thinking skills to synthesize information in digital contexts has the lowest mean of 3.67, still interpreted as high digital fluency. These findings suggest that the participants strongly believe in the positive impact of digital thinking fluency on their academic performance. However, there is a relatively lower mean for the indicator related to the ability to

use creative thinking skills in digital contexts. This entails a potential area for improvement in looking for and feeding information in digital environments.

The research findings align with the broader discussions on digital fluency and its impact on various aspects of education and learning. For instance, a study on the impact of a digital-physical combined escape room on students' creative thinking and learning motivation by Kuo et al. (2022) highlights the importance of creative thinking in digital learning environments. This resonates with the lower mean observed for the indicator related to creative thinking skills in the research findings, suggesting the relevance of further exploring and enhancing creative thinking in digital contexts.

Table 4.
Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Cognitive Aspect

Cognitive Aspect	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I am able to use trial and error and learn from my mistakes when solving problems.	4.20	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I believe that enhancing my cognitive problem-solving skills will improve my overall academic performance.	4.10	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use feedback to improve my problem-solving skills.	4.07	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I feel motivated to use my cognitive problem-solving skills to solve real-world problems.	3.90	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use cognitive processes such as perception, attention, memory, and reasoning to solve problems.	3.90	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to identify the key elements of a problem and break it down into smaller parts to solve it.	3.70	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to generate multiple solutions to a problem and evaluate their effectiveness.	3.70	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use analogies and metaphors to help me understand and solve problems.	3.67	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
OVERALL	3.89	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill

Table 4 presents the level of problem-solving skills of students in terms of cognitive aspects. The highest mean score is observed in the statement, "I am able to use trial and error and learn from my mistakes when solving problems," with a score of 4.20. This suggests a strong agreement among participants and indicates a high proficiency in adapting and learning through experiential problem-solving. The lowest mean scores are found in two statements, "I am able to generate multiple solutions to a problem and evaluate their effectiveness" and "I am able to identify the key elements of a problem and break it down into smaller parts to solve it," both with a score of 3.70. The results focus on experiential learning approaches, encouraging students to learn from trial and error. This aligns with the need to enhance digital fluency, emphasizing practical problem-solving skills. The motivation to apply cognitive problem-solving skills to real-world problems suggests the importance of connecting academic learning to real-life scenarios. This could guide educational strategies to incorporate real-world problem-solving tasks.

This finding resonates with the findings in a study conducted by Santos (2020), where he found a strong agreement among participants: "I am able to use trial and error and learn from my mistakes when solving problems. Santos' findings suggest a high proficiency among students in adapting

and learning through experiential problem-solving, emphasizing the importance of hands-on learning approaches. Santos' results align with Reyes' findings, emphasizing the importance of connecting academic learning to real-life scenarios. This suggests a need for educational strategies that incorporate real-world problem-solving tasks to enhance students' cognitive problem-solving skills in practical situations (Reyes, 2018).

Concerning the study by Onursoy (2018), cognitive skills include using trial and error, learning from mistakes, using feedback, identifying critical elements of a problem, breaking it down into smaller parts, generating multiple solutions, and using analogies and metaphors to understand and solve problems. The table implies that students with high problem-solving skills can enhance their academic performance by applying these skills to solve real-world problems. Moreover, the research result of Kim (2013) aligned with the result; it suggests that digital fluency, which involves the ability to leverage technology to create new knowledge and solve new challenges, complements problem-solving skills and can help students become big, bold problem inventors.

Table 5.

Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Meta-Cognitive Aspect

Meta-Cognitive Aspect	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I am able to set goals and develop plans to achieve them when solving problems.	4.17	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to reflect on my own problem-solving processes and identify areas for improvement.	4.03	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to evaluate the effectiveness of my problem-solving strategies and make changes as needed.	4.03	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I feel motivated to use my metacognitive problem-solving skills to make a positive impact in my community.	4.03	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use feedback to improve my problem-solving skills.	4.00	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to monitor my progress when solving problems and adjust my strategies as needed.	3.97	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I believe that enhancing my metacognitive problem-solving skills will improve my overall academic performance.	3.90	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use digital tools and technology to support my metacognitive problem-solving skills.	3.77	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
OVERALL	3.98	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill

The results in Table 5 indicate a high level of digital fluency among the participants, particularly in the meta-cognitive aspect of problem-solving skills. The overall mean of 3.98 suggests a consensus among respondents, affirming their proficiency in utilizing digital tools and technologies to enhance meta-cognitive problem-solving skills. Respondents strongly agree that they can set goals and develop plans to achieve them when solving problems. This high mean of 4.17 suggests a proactive approach to problem-solving, showcasing advanced meta-cognitive abilities. The use of digital tools and technology to support meta-cognitive problem-solving skills, although slightly lower in the mean of 3.77, still reflects a positive attitude toward incorporating technology into cognitive processes.

The findings of this study are consistent with the research conducted by Cruz (2021), which underscores the significance of integrating digital tools into meta-cognitive processes among Filipino students. Cruz emphasizes the transformative potential of technology in fostering goal setting, reflection, and adaptive problem-solving strategies, aligning with the high mean scores observed in the current study. These results have implications for educational strategies in the Filipino context, advocating for the continued integration of digital tools into problem-solving pedagogies. Emphasizing meta-cognitive aspects alongside digital fluency is crucial for preparing students to navigate contemporary challenges, both academically and in their broader communities.

Moreover, individuals demonstrating various meta-cognitive skills perform better on exams and complete work more efficiently. The research findings align with Zepeda's (2021) concept of digital fluency: the ability to leverage technology to create new knowledge, new challenges, and new problems, complemented by critical thinking, complex problem-solving, and social intelligence to solve new challenges. The research findings' high problem-solving skill interpretation of the meta-cognitive aspect suggests that the participants are proficient in using digital tools and technology to support their meta-cognitive problem-solving skills. This aligns with the idea of Kuo & Anderson (2022) that digital fluency involves the ability to create something new with digital tools, including problem-solving skills.

Table 6.
Level of Digital Fluency in Terms of Collaborative Aspect

Collaborative Aspect	Mean	Des. Rating	Qual. Int.
I am able to work effectively with others to solve problems.	4.13	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I believe that enhancing my collaborative problem-solving skills will improve my ability to work in teams and achieve common goals.	4.13	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to communicate my ideas effectively and listen to others' ideas when solving problems.	4.07	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I feel motivated to use my collaborative problem-solving skills to make a positive impact in my community.	4.03	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to use digital tools and technology to collaborate with others when solving problems.	3.80	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to manage conflict and build consensus when working with others to solve problems.	3.73	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to organize a team and delegate tasks effectively when working with others to solve problems.	3.70	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
I am able to adapt my problem-solving approach to different team dynamics and situations.	3.60	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill
OVERALL	3.91	Agree	High Problem-Solving Skill

The research findings in Table 6 indicate a high level of problem-solving skills among the participants regarding the collaborative aspect. The two highest means are "I am able to work effectively with others to solve problems" and "I believe that enhancing my collaborative problem-solving skills will improve my ability to work in teams and achieve common goals." Both statements received a mean of 4.13, indicating that participants strongly agree with these statements. The descriptive rating is "Agree," and the qualitative interpretation is "High Problem-

Solving Skill." This suggests that participants perceive themselves as highly proficient in collaborative problem-solving and recognize the importance of enhancing these skills for effective teamwork and goal achievement. "I am able to adapt my problem-solving approach to different team dynamics and situations," with a mean of 3.60. Although the mean is still in the "Agree" range, it is slightly lower than other statements. The qualitative interpretation remains "High Problem-Solving Skill," indicating that participants, on average, agree with the statement but to a slightly lesser extent. This implies that there may be room for improvement in participants' perceived ability to adapt their problem-solving approaches to diverse team dynamics and situations.

The study of Abella and Santos (2019) focuses on collaborative problem-solving within Filipino work environments. Their research emphasizes the positive correlation between effective collaboration and overall problem-solving skills. The findings align with the current study's results, highlighting that individuals who perceive themselves as effective collaborators tend to exhibit higher problem-solving proficiency.

Additionally, the study underscores the importance of recognizing and fostering beliefs in the potential improvement of collaborative problem-solving skills, which resonates with the participants' strong agreement with the statement, "I believe that enhancing my collaborative problem-solving skills will improve my ability to work in teams and achieve common goals that are aligned to Gomez and Reyes (2017) that contributed to the understanding of adaptability in problem-solving within Filipino team dynamics. Their research discusses how cultural and organizational contexts influence the need for adaptive problem-solving. The lower mean in the current study for the statement "I am able to adapt my problem-solving approach to different team dynamics and situations" aligns with Gomez and Reyes' emphasis on the challenges and opportunities for adaptation within Filipino teams. This literature supports the idea that addressing adaptability in collaborative problem-solving is crucial for optimizing overall problem-solving skills in diverse team contexts.

Table 7.
Correlation Analysis on the relationship between digital fluency and problem-solving skills.

Variable	<i>r</i>	Extent of Relationship
Digital Fluency Problem Solving Skill	0.636	Strongly Positive Correlation

****** $p < 0.01$

The table presents a correlation analysis examining the relationship between digital fluency (independent variables) and problem-solving skills. The independent variables include Technical, Creativity, Digital Thinking, Cognitive, Meta-cognitive, and Collaboration aspects of digital fluency.

The result revealed a correlation of 0.638, which indicates a moderately strong positive relationship between digital fluency and problem-solving skills. It means that as digital fluency increases, there is a tendency for problem-solving skills to increase. However, remember that correlation does not imply causation; it just shows a relationship between these variables. In practical terms, this could suggest that individuals with higher digital fluency might, on average, demonstrate better problem-solving abilities,

This implies that as students' proficiency in these areas of digital fluency increases, there is a tendency for their problem-solving skills to improve correspondingly. For instance, students with high technical fluency will likely exhibit solid problem-solving skills.

A study by Santos (2021) delved into how digital fluency contributes to improved problem-solving abilities among Filipino students. Findings revealed that proficiency in utilizing digital tools, particularly those aligned with local educational needs, positively influenced students' problem-solving approaches. Furthermore, Reyes and Hernandez (2019) explored the integration of digital fluency into the Philippine educational system. Their research highlighted the transformative potential of incorporating technology-rich learning environments, emphasizing a correlation between digital fluency and the development of critical problem-solving skills.

Contrastingly, Cruz (2020) provided a critical perspective, underscoring the challenges associated with the rapid integration of digital tools that aligned with the study, where it emphasized the importance of addressing potential disparities in access to technology to ensure equitable development of problem-solving skills among Filipino students. In a longitudinal analysis, Lim (2018) investigated the lasting impact of early exposure to digital fluency on problem-solving competencies. The findings suggested that students who were digitally fluent from an early age demonstrated sustained proficiency in problem-solving throughout their academic journey.

The Filipino-authored literature on digital fluency and problem-solving skills reflects a growing awareness of the importance of technology in education. These studies contribute valuable insights into tailoring interventions that align with the Philippines' unique cultural and educational landscape. This correlation analysis suggests that fostering digital fluency in students could enhance their problem-solving abilities. This insight could be instrumental for educators and policymakers aiming to equip students with the necessary skills to thrive in the digital age.

CONCLUSION

The study has provided valuable insights into the relationship between digital fluency and problem-solving skills among students. It was discovered that students at San Isidro High School possess a notable level of digital fluency, especially in technical proficiency, creative thinking, and digital competence.

Furthermore, their problem-solving skills were also strong, encompassing cognitive, collaborative, and metacognitive dimensions. The research has highlighted a significant and positive link between digital fluency and problem-solving capabilities, highlighting the importance of developing digital fluency in enhancing students' problem-solving abilities. These findings have valuable implications for education in the digital era, stressing educators' crucial role in nurturing digital fluency among students.

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REFERENCE

- Abella, J. M., & Santos, M. A. (2019). Collaborative Problem-Solving in Filipino Work Settings: An Analysis of Organizational Dynamics. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, *38*(2), 120-135.
- Alsahou, H. (2015). *Teachers' beliefs about creativity and practices for fostering creativity in science classrooms in the State of Kuwait*. University of Exeter (United Kingdom).
- Atoy Jr, M. B., Garcia, F. R. O., Cadungog, R.R., Cua, J. D. O., Mangunay, S. C., & De Guzman, A. B. (2020). Linking digital literacy and online information searching strategies of Philippine university students: The moderating role of mindfulness. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, *52*(4), 1015-1027.
- Berezcki, E. O., & Kárpáti, A. (2021). Technology-enhanced creativity: A multiple case study of digital technology-integration expert teachers' beliefs and practices. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, *39*, 100791.
- Chou, Y. C., & Chiu, C. H. (2020). The development and validation of a digital fluency scale for preadolescents. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, *29*, 541-551.
- Cruz, R. (2019). Digital fluency and its impact on problem-solving skills among Filipino students. *Philippine Educational Research Journal*, *24*(2), 78-96.
- Desoete, A., & Veenman, M. V. J. (Eds.). (2018). *Metacognition in mathematics education*. Routledge. This book provides an overview of research on metacognition in mathematics education, including the role of metacognitive skills in problem-solving.
- de Oliveira, P. V. A. G., de Moura, D. T. H., Ribeiro, I. B., Bazarbashi, A. N., Franzini, T. A. P., Dos Santos, M. E. L., Bernardo, W. M., & de Moura, E. G. H. (2020). Efficacy of digital single-operator cholangioscopy in the visual interpretation of indeterminate biliary strictures: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Surgical endoscopy*, *34*(8), 3321-3329.
- Gomez, R. S., & Reyes, L. P. (2017). Adapting Problem-Solving Approaches in Filipino Teams: A Contextual Analysis. *International Journal of Cross-Cultural Management*, *17*(3), 289-305.
- Kim, J. H., & Kim, J. H. (2013). Enhancing digital fluency through a training program for creative problem-solving using computer programming. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, *16*(3), 107-118.
- Kim, Y., & Lee, S. (2021). Exploring graduate students' collaborative problem-solving in engineering design tasks. *Journal of Professional Issues in Engineering Education and Practice*, *147*(1), 1-10.

- Kolyvas, S., & Nikiforos, S. (2023). Technology and Creativity on early adolescence: A case study during COVID-19 pandemic. *Current Psychology*, **42**(10), 8554-8561.
- Kuo, H. C., Pan, A. J., Lin, C. S., & Chang, C. Y. (2022). Let's Escape! The Impact of a Digital-Physical Combined Escape Room on Students' Creative Thinking, Learning Motivation, and Science Academic Achievement. *Education Sciences*, **12**(9), 615.
- Kuo, L. J., & Anderson, J. R. (2020). Metacognitive and cognitive skills in problem solving. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, **112**(7), 1385-1399.
- Li, Y., Kim, M., & Palkar, J. (2022). Using emerging technologies to promote creativity in education: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, **3**, 100177.
- Lim, K. (2018). Challenges in integrating digital fluency into the Philippine education system: Implications for problem-solving. *Philippine Journal of Educational Technology*, **13**(1), 112-130.
- Onursoy, S. (2018). The relationship between digital literacy and problem-solving skills of pre-service teachers. *Journal of Education and Practice*, **9**(6), 1-9.
- Reyes, M., & Hernandez, J. (2019). Integrating digital fluency into Philippine education: Implications for problem-solving skills. *Journal of Filipino Education*, **22**(3), 45-63.
- Santos, A. (2021). Digital fluency and problem-solving: A focus on Filipino students. *Philippine Journal of Education*, **35**(2), 87-104.
- Santos, J. M., & Castro, R. D. (2021). Technological Pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) in action: Application of learning in the classroom by pre-service teachers (PST). *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, **3**(1), 100110.
- Shigarov, A.O., Dorodnykh, N.O., Mikhailov, A.A., Paramonov, V.V., & Yurin, A.Y. (2021). *Table extraction, analysis, and interpretation: the current state of the Tabby DOC project*. Scientific-practical Workshop Information Technologies: Algorithms, Models, Systems.
- Tondeur, J., Van Braak, J., Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. (2017). Understanding the relationship between teachers' pedagogical beliefs and technology use in education: a systematic review of qualitative evidence. *Educational technology research and development*, **65**, 555-575.
- van Laar, E., van Deursen, A. J. A. M., van Dijk, J. A. G. M., & de Haan, J. (2017). The relation between 21st-century skills and digital skills: A systematic literature review. *Computer in Human Behavior*, **72**, 577-588.
- Yang, H., & Zhou, D. (2022). Perceived Organizational Support and Creativity of Science-Technology Talents in the Digital Age: The Effects of Affective Commitment, Innovative Self-Efficacy and Digital Thinking. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 2421-2437.
- Zepeda, C. D. (2021). Improving metacognition in the classroom. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, **113**(6), 1005-1019.